

Reporting template

Title of case study

Main authors

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With contributions from

Name of reviewers

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Reporting template for the in-depth case study research

EXPLANATORY NOTE

As described in the research guideline, filling in the reporting template is the final phase of the in-depth case study work. This template should be filled in based on all the data you have been collecting. You will need to move from your individual interviews, focus groups and workshops to a higher level of analysis in order to answer all the questions in the reporting template.

The reporting template is structured according to the five interactions as described in the analytical framework. Underneath each interaction we have structured our questioning according to a structural, functional and system failure/merit analysis (see reporting template).

In the template you will find the general research question or topic we want to discuss. Under this research question you will firstly find some small instruction text in grey. This text provides you with information on what exactly we want you to talk about. In the accompanying **Excel-file 'Your case study process'**, we have provided some examples of interview questions you can use to find an answer to the research question. These are, however, only suggestions/inspiration. It is not a problem if you want to address the question differently or if you need to nuance it according to the context or language in which you are working. Please delete the grey text once you have completed a section.

Before starting we kindly ask you to read though the following practical information carefully!

- The case study work builds on and further elaborates the information collected in the **'light-touch' reviews**. Use the data you collected during the 'light-touch' reviews as a starting point. The links with questions from the 'light-touch' review templates are indicated where needed.
- In the reporting template we sometimes use tabular overviews and/or charts. The tables are often only meant to get a quick first overview; identifying the key issues. The most important is the discussion of the main issues below each table.
- Sections for 'additional issues specific to the case study' allow you to include information that you consider relevant but does not fit in the other sections of the template.
- It is very important to provide empirical evidence with **explicit references** to methods and sources of data. The most important sources of information will be expert interviews, results from workshops and/or focus groups, case study meetings, official statistics ... (**Do NOT base your answers on your own best professional judgment**). Please include a **good number of quotes** from key actors/practitioners/stakeholders to show the link between the conclusions and the data. We also encourage you to add **graphical material** such as photos, schemes ...
- Refer to other studies wherever helpful (with complete references, please).
- The **concluding section is very important** as it relates the main results of your case study back to our overarching research interests and project goal.
- Overall, we should aim at **approximately 35 pages**, not more (if needed plus appendices for background data); so make sure reporting is **succinct, to the point and evidence-based**.
- We will organise **an internal review process to assure a high quality of reporting templates**. As these templates are the basis for cross-comparison and the drafting of Case Study Portraits, please keep this in mind when writing.

1 INTRODUCTION: DEFINING THE STUDIED INNOVATION SYSTEMS

Max. 3 pages

We advise you to write this introductory section as one of the last things you do when finishing this reporting template. You can check these three key questions with your case study respondents, e.g. by formulating some introductory questions (examples in the excel file). Furthermore, please have a look at the 'light-touch' reviews first, because the questions are very similar. Try to summarise the answers on the relevant 'light-touch' review questions and propose this to your respondent. "Is it correct that your project is about ...?" We expect more detail and precision here than in the 'light-touch' reviews.

1.1 WHAT IS THE CASE STUDY ABOUT AND WHO ARE THE KEY ACTORS?

Please give a short introduction about the case study; its history, the multi-actor partnership and the key actors within this case study. You can also elaborate on key actors that were (are) not formally part of the multi-actor partnership but did have an important influence. We would like you to also include the objective of the partnership and reflect upon the societal challenge they are addressing.

1.2 WHAT TYPE OF INNOVATION ARE THEY AIMING AT?

Please explain what is innovative about this case. Here we would like to learn more about:

- Where the interactive innovation case is positioned in terms of innovation spiral phase (initial idea, inspiration, planning, development, realisation, dissemination, embedding). This can mean explaining that they have moved through all these phases, or only some, or that they are still planning to take it further.
- Are we dealing with a technical, organisational, social ... innovation?
- Whether the case perceives their innovation to be rather radical or more incremental¹.
- Which type of innovation or combination of types they are undertaking or planning to undertake. Where there any 'unexpected' innovations?

It is possible that for your case study not all these bullets are relevant. Please make an informed choice on which points are most relevant to report on.

1.3 WHAT IS THE CONTEXT IN WHICH THE CASE STUDY OPERATES?

Please explain the different types of context of which the case study is part. We would like to learn more about:

- The geographical scale;
- The languages that are spoken by the relevant actors (both formal languages and jargon);
- The economic scale (multiple sectors, scale for possible deployment ...);
- The policy context (part of a programme or not);
- Etc.

It is possible that for your case study not all these bullets are relevant. Please make an informed choice on which points are most relevant on which to report. You can also use the Task 1.3 report on the pathways for innovation support to provide a better contextualisation of your case.

¹ This is related to the degree of change that the implementation of the innovation induces into practice, the radical and disruptive or more incremental (Narayanan and O'Connor 2010, OECD Oslo Manual 2005). Radical innovation thus implies a fundamental redesign or major improvements, while incremental innovation are more minor improvements or tweaks to existing products, processes, practices etc.

2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Max. 1 page

Description of the methods applied (interviews of various kinds, data and document analysis, workshops and focus groups etc.).

More concretely, we expect to see here the following information:

- **Desk research:** *which reports/websites/documents/reports did you use? Please also keep track of them in the reference section at the end of this reporting template.*
- **In-depth interviews:**
 - *How many in-depth interviews did you do?*
 - *Who were the respondents? (types of respondents, not the names).*
 - *How did you select your respondents?*
 - *When and where did the interviews take place?*
 - *Were there any difficulties/challenges in conducting the interviews?*
 - *How did you decide that sufficient interviews were made?*
 - *How did you process the in-depth interviews? (i.e. from recording to interview summary).*
- **Focus groups:**
 - *Did you organise a focus group?*
 - *What was the objective of the focus group in your case study research?*
 - *How many persons participated?*
 - *Which type of respondents were participating? (end-users, project partners ...)*
 - *How were they selected?*
 - *When and where did the focus group take place?*
 - *Which methodology did you use in the focus group and why?*
 - *Were there any difficulties in carrying out the focus group?*
 - *How did you process the focus groups? (i.e. from recording to focus group summary).*

3 FINDINGS FOR INTERACTION 1

The major objectives of the research related to this interaction are to:

1. Explore the different strategies of a partnership in the search for funding (private or public) and how they take into account economic considerations, the market and risk(s);
2. Identify the (public or private) funding mechanisms and to explore the roles they play in the interactive innovation cases;
3. Examine to what extent and how the capacity of a (public or private) funding body affects the functioning of the interactive innovation case;
4. Understand the links between funding mechanisms and higher-level strategies or programmes.

The chronological structure of this interaction is represented in Figure 1. Interactively building a timeline with the respondents might help you to structure your interview. This timeline should summarise the most important points related to the first interaction.

Figure 1. Timeline representing the chronological structure of interaction 1

3.1 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

3.1.1 Who are the key actors² in this interaction?

Please fill in the table below. The key actors in this interaction can be both formally and directly involved in the interactive innovation case, or can be considered a 'stakeholder', meaning individuals/persons or groups served by, affected by, or with a legitimate interest (or stake) at a certain moment in time in the interactive innovation case ([LIAISON Glossary](#)). You can start with the 'light-touch' review results and then continue with your additional gathered data. In this first interaction the 'stakeholders' are limited to those actors that have played a role in securing the funding or financing.

Actor types	More specifically:	Name of organisation and sector (public or private)	Nature of involvement/Official role
Individual farmers or foresters	<i>e.g. pioneer farmer, organic farmer etc.</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Researchers or R&D departments	<i>e.g. researchers at institutes or universities, R&D departments etc.</i>	<i>e.g. ILVO (public/private)</i>	<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Education	<i>e.g. primary education, (agricultural) schools, universities in their role as educator etc.</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Support organisations	<i>e.g. advisors, representative of supporting organisations, financial actors (banks, venture capital, business angels), network organisations etc.</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Market actors – supply side	<i>e.g. business, suppliers (e.g. raw materials), manufacturers, service providers etc.</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Market actors – demand side	<i>e.g. business, processing or marketing SME, processing or marketing producer organisation, retailers, consumers and their organisations, other companies (B2B)</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Civil society	<i>e.g. NGOs, local community groups, LEADER groups etc.</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Administrative bodies	<i>e.g. local municipality, regional government, national government, ministries, departments, EU institutions etc.</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>
Others (please specify)	<i>any type of actor that does not fit with the types from above</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials etc.</i>

² When referring here to 'actors', this implies 'innovation actors', i.e.: groups of people who are involved in innovation projects and initiatives in the agri-food or forestry sector - farmers, farm workers, agricultural educators, researchers, non-academic experts, public and independent private advisors, supply chain actors and other actors in agriculture to harness knowledge and information from various sources for improved livelihoods ([LIAISON Glossary](#)).

3.1.2 Why are these the key actors in this interaction? Are there any actors missing?

Please explain in a few sentences why these are the key actors in this interaction and who makes this argumentation (is it you as the researcher, was it your contact person, were they multiple respondents?)

This question can be answered while doing the timeline exercise. You have to ask constantly when certain changes happened or milestones were reached who was involved and why.

3.1.3 What are the key formal institutions framing this first interaction?

Please fill in the table below. Institutions are commonly known as ‘the rules of the game’ or ‘code of conduct’ (Woolthuis et al., 2005). You can start with the ‘light-touch’ review results and continue.

Institutions framing the interactions	At the programme level	At the interactive innovation case level
Formal Formal and tangible rules such as laws, regulations, contracts, standards, product specifications and property rights (Woolthuis et al., 2005).	Any rules or regulations that are written down and can be enforced e.g. guidelines, administrative requirements etc.	Any type of signed document. This can be a consortium agreement, contract, formal code of conduct, product specifications etc.

Why did you include these institutions here?

Please explain the reasons behind this choice and who is making this argumentation (is it you as the researcher, was it your contact person, were they multiple respondents?)

3.1.4 How would the different actors of the interactive innovation case characterise the relationship with the funding body or the investors?

With this question we are trying to find out which the more informal institutions are that influence this first interaction. Informal institutions influence social and economic life in a subtle often intangible way (Coenen and Diaz Lopez, 2010). Examples are trust, habits, norms, values, beliefs, types of behaviours traditions, routines and preferences. This can be very subjective and might differ from one respondent to another. Some more questions you could ask to answer this question are provided in the excel file.

3.2 FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

3.2.1 How did the interactive innovation case learn about (public or private) opportunities for funding?

Please explain how the case study actors came to learn about the funding opportunity. Was it a general call for proposals, an open call by a funding mechanism, via a networking event etc. You can start from the answers from the ‘light-touch’ review questionnaire, for more inspiration on how to ask this in an interview, you can consult the excel file.

3.2.2 Why did the case study choose to pursue this type of funding? Were there any other funding mechanisms which could have been relevant to the case study?

For publicly funded initiatives: Please explain the reasons the case study actors identify for applying for this particular type of funding and not another one. You can also expand on whether they also considered other types of funding, or if they would pursue this type of funding again if they could make the decision again.

For privately funded initiatives you can elaborate on whether they undertook any previous unsuccessful application(s) and why they chose to fund the idea/project/... with private funding.

3.2.3 For publicly funded initiatives: How did the application process for funding influence the process of the interactive innovation case?

Please explain here the way in which the case study actors see the influence of the application process on their initiative. This can include the time between the application and the allocation of the funding, but also the way they had to organise their initiative or how they 'sold' it to the funding authority etc.

3.2.4 What are the (dis)advantages of the current funding instrument of the case study?

Please explain what the case study actors perceive to be the main (dis)advantages of the funding instrument they are currently using. You could also elaborate on whether other flexible funding sources were available or how they would adapt the instrument to better fit their needs.

3.2.5 For privately funded initiatives: How did the financier make the decision to invest in this interactive innovation case?

Please explain here the decision-making process to use private funds or no external funds. You can include here:

- Who made the decision to use private financing?
- Which risks were assessed in this process?
- Was it an intentional process, or did it grow more organically? (e.g. was an innovation intended?)
- What was at stake for the actors involved or other stakeholders?

3.2.6 Besides the provision of funding or financing, was there another type of involvement by the funding body, investing business, or other type of organisational set-up in the interactive innovation process? If yes, which one?

Please explain whether or not the funding body (or people at the funding body) were involved at any point in time in the internal case study work. The answer to this question should include the perceptions of the actors that are formally part of the interactive innovation case, not that of the people at the funding body as long as they are not a partner in the case study. This could include any review or inputs on the application or any lobbying that was done by case study actors beforehand in order to learn about potential interests of the funding body, but also whether there was any further involvement after the allocation of the funding.

3.2.7 In case of public or mixed funding: What is the aim of the funding mechanism the interactive innovation case applied for? Is it part of a higher-level (business) strategy, programme or policy framework?

Please explain the context and aim of the funding mechanism, what is the logic behind it, which other types of cases are funded by it etc. Please explain in which higher level strategy, programme or policy framework the funding mechanism is framed (if any). What is the programme or political strategy behind? Are there any higher-level objectives set?

Please see also the results of [Task 1.3 report](#) on the pathways for innovation support. Please make any additions to this information based upon your consultation with interviewees and respondents from the in-depth case study if needed.

3.2.8 How were economic considerations related to the process of innovation and the concerned actors (e.g. market situation, risks, economic feasibility) taken into account?

Please explain how the economic realities in terms of their own market or socio-economic situation, their risks, economic feasibility of the different types of actors were taken into account, if at all. You can also include answers that deal with how this could possibly solve this issue.

3.3 GOOD PRACTICES AND FAILURES

3.3.1 For publicly or mixed funded initiatives: How did the actors of the interactive innovation case experience the selection and evaluation procedures for the procurement of the funding?

Please explain the experiences of the case study actors with the application process, both experiences related to how the process was managed by the case study actors and how it was managed by the funding body. Answers could include references to the proposal writing process, the administrative requirements, the application procedure or online platform, but also the transparency of the selection procedures, i.e. was the evaluation procedure fair, did they agree with the feedback received?

3.3.2 For privately funded initiatives: How did the different participants in the interactive innovation case experience the investment risks?

Please explain from the point of view of the participants in the interactive innovation case how they experienced the investment risks. Answers here can include explaining who invested how much or what and who had the highest stakes.

3.3.3 To what extent do the actors of the interactive innovation case think that the amount and type of funding they secured is reasonable with the expectations set by the funding agency/investor? Why (not)?

Please explain whether case study actors felt that the expectations related to the funding were in balance with the amount and type of funding they have secured. Also elaborate on the reasons behind their argumentation.

3.3.4 If your case is implemented under a project format: How suitable was the 'project' cooperation format for reaching the main objectives of the case?

Please explain what the case study actors think about the project as a way of working together and how it helped (if at all) in reaching the objectives set in the interactive innovation case. You could also elaborate on which format they would have preferred to work in or how they would like to cooperate in the future.

3.3.5 How does the funding body or private investor perceive its role in the interactive innovation cases?

Please explain how the officials (e.g. project officer, policy officer) from the relevant funding body understand the way in which they are helping the project/network/initiative to move forward in their work. This could include answers to questions such as: Do they think that they are able to provide the best support available or are they more critical of their own work? Are there any things they would improve or change? Why (not)? Do they have the right capacities and skills available to bring it to a good end? What could help them? You can also have a look at the excel file for additional ideas for interview questions.

3.3.6 If the funding mechanism, investing business, or other type of organisational set-up for funding is part of a higher-level strategy or policy framework: How are the programmes or higher-level strategies translated into this funding mechanism?

Please explain how the higher-level objectives of programmes or strategies have been translated into a funding mechanism, by elaborating on the actors or institutions involved, possible bottlenecks or barriers, good practices and whether there is any space for adapting these programmes or strategies when necessary.

3.4 CASE STUDY SPECIFIC ISSUES

If there are any other concerns or interesting points related to the first interaction for which you could not find any place under the previous questions, please write them down here.

4 FINDINGS FOR INTERACTION 2: INTERACTIONS WITHIN THE INTERACTIVE INNOVATION CASE

The major objectives of the research related to this interaction are to:

1. Identify the actors within the case and to understand their relationships with each other;
2. Understand what motivates and convinces actors to participate in a multi-actor partnership;
3. Understand how actors formed and maintained their partnership and formed boundaries around it (i.e. who is in and who is out);
4. Understand how differences in capacities, knowledge, power and agency influence the dynamics of interaction in the case;
5. Identify good practices in interactive innovation partnerships.

An example of the chronological structure of this interaction is represented below. Interactively building a timeline with the respondents might help you to structure your interview. This timeline should summarise the most important points related to the second interaction.

4.1 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

4.1.1 Who are the key actors³ in this interaction?

Please fill in the table below. You can add or delete rows in order to adapt the table to your case study. The key actors in this interaction are only those which are formally and directly involved in the interactive innovation case. You can start with the 'light-touch' review results and then continue with your additional gathered data.

Actor types	More specifically:	Name of organisation and sector (public or private)	Nature of involvement/Official role
Individual farmers or foresters	<i>e.g. pioneer farmer, organic farmer</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Researchers or R&D departments	<i>e.g. researchers at institutes or universities, R&D departments</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Education	<i>e.g. primary education, (agricultural) schools, universities in their role as educator</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Support organisations	<i>e.g. advisors, representative of supporting organisations, financial actors (banks, venture capital, business angels), network organisations</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Market actors – supply side	<i>e.g. business, suppliers (e.g. raw materials), manufacturers, service providers</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Market actors – demand side	<i>e.g. business, processing or marketing SME, processing or marketing producer organisation, retailers, consumers and their organisations, other companies (B2B)</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Civil society	<i>e.g. NGOs, local community groups, LEADER groups</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Administrative bodies	<i>e.g. local municipality, regional government, national government, ministries, departments, EU institutions</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Others (please specify)	<i>any type of actors that does not fit with the types from above</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>

³ When referring here to 'actors', this implies 'innovation actors', i.e. groups of people who are involved in innovation projects and initiatives in the agri-food or forestry sector - farmers, farm workers, agricultural educators, researchers, non-academic experts, public and independent private advisors, supply chain actors, and other actors in agriculture to harness knowledge and information from various sources for improved livelihoods ([LIAISON Glossary](#)).

4.1.2 Why are these the key actors in this interaction? Are there any missing?

Please explain in a few sentences why these are the key actors in this interaction and who makes this argumentation (is it you as the researcher, was it your contact person, were they multiple respondents?) Check the question in the 'light-touch' review about how actors were involved in the partnership. These questions can be asked when you are doing a timeline exercise.

4.1.3 What are the main characteristics of the actors with regard to working in co-creation?

Please fill in the table below for every individual actor involved in the interactive innovation case. You can copy the table and continue the numbering if there are more than five individual actors. The table can be filled in by each person themselves, or you can ask other key informants to give their impressions about other actors in the case.

Characteristics	Actor 1	Actor 2	Actor 3	Actor 4	Actor 5
Actor type (based upon previous table)					
Professional title	<i>e.g. PhD student</i>				
Sector/background	<i>e.g. biology</i>				
Official project role	<i>e.g. WP leader</i>				
Experience with co-creation	<i>e.g. no prior experience</i>				
Language	<i>e.g. Dutch as mother tongue, good English skills</i>				
Other (please specify)					

4.1.4 What are the key institutions framing the second interaction?

Please fill in the table below. Institutions are commonly known as 'the rules of the game' or 'code of conduct'.

Institutions framing the interactions	At the programme level	At the interactive innovation case level
Formal <i>formal and tangible rules such as laws, regulations, contracts, standards, product specifications and property rights (Woolthuis et al., 2005).</i>	<i>Any rules or regulations that are written down and can be enforced, e.g. guidelines, administrative requirements.</i>	<i>Any type of signed document. This can be a consortium agreement, contract, formal code of conduct, product specifications etc.</i>

4.1.5 How would the interactive innovation case characterise the relationship between the different partners?

With this question we are trying to find out which are the more informal institutions that influence this first interaction. Informal institutions influence social and economic life in a subtle often intangible way (Coenen and Diaz Lopez, 2010). Examples are trust, habits, norms, values, beliefs, types of behaviours traditions, routines and preferences. This can be very subjective and might differ from one respondent to another. Some more questions you could use are provided in the excel file.

4.2 FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

4.2.1 How did the interactive innovation process evolve over time?

Please explain the different important milestones in the interactive innovation process starting from the initiation of the partnership or previous contacts up until the current day. You can add rows to the table.

Please make sure to include who initiated the process, and how other actors got involved and what their relationship is to one another.

If any actors were excluded or if some refused participation, this is also interesting to highlight here.

Be sure to check the 'light-touch' review questionnaire for information, also the excel file gives some tips on questions you can ask respondents to fill in this table.

Milestone no.	Timing	Description

4.2.2 What type of roles do the different actors occupy in the interactive innovation case and why?

Please elaborate on the role of the different actors included in the interactive innovation case. These are not the formal roles as described in the previous section, but rather informal, organically grown: e.g. coordinator, facilitator, intermediary, broker, thought leader etc. Please specify them for each actor you interviewed, or when certain roles for other actors very clearly came across in talking to other actors. This question can be answered by each actor for themselves, but you can also ask key informants in the case study to answer it for others. It is possible that you are not able to complete this exercise for all actors. You can add rows at the end of the table. The excel file also gives some tips on possible interview questions.

Actor type	Role(s) taken up in the interactive innovation case?	Reasoning behind

Are there any roles missing? Why (not)?

Please explain whether there were certain roles which could have been useful to the interactive innovation process but were not taken up. The excel file also gives some tips on possible interview questions.

4.2.3 Which were the objectives or motivation of the participation of the different actors?

In order to understand how actors are mobilised and motivated, we would like you to describe briefly why the actor is involved, what are his/her objectives, i.e. what is in it for them? The excel file also gives some tips on possible interview questions.

Actor type	Objectives or motivation behind the participation in the partnership	To which extent are they fulfilled or confirmed during the implementation of the project/network/initiative?
		<i>not at all, to a limited extent, to some extent, to a great extent, fully (please choose what is applicable)</i>
		<i>not at all, to a limited extent, to some extent, to a great extent, fully (please choose what is applicable)</i>
		<i>not at all, to a limited extent, to some extent, to a great extent, fully (please choose what is applicable)</i>
		<i>not at all, to a limited extent, to some extent, to a great extent, fully (please choose what is applicable)</i>
		<i>not at all, to a limited extent, to some extent, to a great extent, fully (please choose what is applicable)</i>

4.2.4 How are the decision-making processes set up within the interactive innovation case? What did the actors of the multi-actor partnership think about the arrangements?

Please describe the organisational and decision-making process within the interactive innovation case. This could include different types of procedures, the organisation of meetings, whether one actor takes charge of this or if it is more open etc. but also who took charge or which persons' opinions were heard or taken into account ... Some additional questions you can ask during interviews or focus group are given in the excel file.

4.2.5 Who holds the different types of knowledge and skills and how were they applied in the interactive innovation case?

Please fill in the table below. The scope of this table includes only the actors that are formally part of the interactive innovation case.

For the 'when' question: you could use the milestones identified under interaction 1, or just indicate whether it was at the beginning of the case or only in the end, or for example that it was relevant during field trials or project meetings.

For the 'how' question: here we would like to know more how they shared their knowledge or skill set with others. This can be that they had a formal PowerPoint presentation or made a booklet, or it can be more learning by doing, e.g. during a participatory session or in setting up a living laboratory.

Knowledge sources	More specifically (please specify the actor)	Type of knowledge/skill (please use the different terms from the previous table)	When was it relevant?	How was it shared?
Individual farmers or foresters		<i>e.g. technical, marketing, management, communication, facilitation, leadership, cooperation and networking, other social skills, any other (specify)</i>		
Researchers or R&D departments				
Education				
Support organisations				
Market actors – supply side				
Market actors – demand side				
Civil society				
Administrative bodies				
Others (please specify)				

Were there any types of knowledge or skills missing? Which ones?

Please explain further which types of knowledge or skills they thought were missing. You can also elaborate on why they feel this way.

4.2.6 How did the different actors learn from each other?

Please explain the way actors in the interactive innovation case learned from each other e.g. using different tools or methods. You could include how knowledge is shared in the interactive innovation case and who learned from who specifically. Did it work well or not? Why do they think this is the case? Would they do it differently the next time?

4.3 GOOD PRACTICES AND FAILURES

4.3.1 How and when were the objectives of the multi-actor partnership set? How were they kept up to date?

Please explain the process towards the setting of the objectives and who was involved or excluded. You can also include whether or not these objectives have remained unchanged or if they can be updated.

4.3.2 How did the partners of the case study feel in terms of being taken into account and heard in the interactive innovation process?

Please explain how the different actors feel the cooperation went. Answers here could include whether the different actors felt like their opinions, knowledge or skills were taken into account, whether the interaction between the partners went smoothly or rather difficult etc. You can find some ideas for questions in the excel file.

4.3.3 What were the three factors underpinning the success of the cooperation? Why?

Please explain and compare the different factors identified by the different types of actors as contributing to the success of the cooperation and why they think these were the factors. Please try to use the actor types we have been applying throughout the reporting template when comparing the factors of success. For example, the two farming organisations in an interactive innovation case identified factors which were completely different from those identified by a research institute. You can then explain the differences.

Please also check the 'light-touch' review questionnaires before interviewing respondents and some additional questions for inspiration in the excel file.

4.3.4 What were the key difficulties in terms of cooperation within the interactive innovation case that had to be overcome? How were they addressed?

Please explain and compare the difficulties identified and why they think these were the key difficulties. We would like to know how the different types of actors of the interactive innovation case think about these difficulties, so please highlight the differences in opinions. We would like to know whether the interactive innovation cases were able to be flexible and adapt to new circumstances and why (not).

Please also check the 'light-touch' review questionnaires before interviewing respondents and some additional questions for inspiration in the excel file.

4.4 CASE STUDY SPECIFIC ISSUES

If there are any other concerns or interesting points related to the second interaction for which you could not find any place under the previous questions, please write them down here.

5 FINDINGS FOR INTERACTION 3

The major objectives of the research related to this interaction are to:

1. Identify the type, timing and objective of the involvement of external stakeholders in interactive innovation cases and how this affects the case;
2. Learn how networks and networking between interactive innovation cases influences their interactive innovation process;
3. Learn about the motivations of external stakeholders in engaging in interactive innovation cases.

An example of the chronological structure of this interaction is represented below. Interactively building a timeline with the respondents might help you to structure your interview. This timeline should summarise the most important points related to the first interaction.

5.1 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

5.1.1 Who are the key actors⁴ in this interaction?

Please fill in the table below. You can find some additional questions to help you fill in the table in the excel file. The key actors in this interaction can be both formally and directly involved in the interactive innovation case, or can be considered a 'stakeholder', meaning individuals/persons or groups served by, affected by, or with a legitimate interest (or stake) at a certain moment in time in the interactive innovation case ([LIAISON Glossary](#)). You can start with the 'light-touch' review results and then continue with your additional gathered data. In this third interaction the 'stakeholders' are those actors that were involved in one way or another in the interactive innovation case (e.g. via networking, stakeholder outreach activities, field trials, surveys, case studies).

Actor types	More specifically:	Name of organisation and sector (public/private) (if possible)	Nature of involvement
Individual farmers or foresters	<i>e.g. pioneer farmer, organic farmer</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Researchers or R&D departments	<i>e.g. researchers at institutes or universities, R&D departments</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Education	<i>e.g. primary education, (agricultural) schools, universities in their role as educator</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Support organisations	<i>e.g. advisors, representative of supporting organisations, financial actors (banks, venture capital, business angels), network organisations</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Market actors – supply side	<i>e.g. business, suppliers (e.g. raw materials), manufacturers, service providers</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Market actors – demand side	<i>e.g. business, processing or marketing SME, processing or marketing producer organisation, retailers, consumers and their organisations, other companies (B2B)</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Civil society	<i>e.g. NGOs, local community groups, LEADER groups</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Administrative bodies	<i>e.g. local municipality, regional government, national government, ministries, departments, EU institutions</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>
Others (please specify)	<i>any type of actor that does not fit with the types from above</i>		<i>e.g. work package leader, project officer at funding body, coordinator, communication, field trials</i>

⁴ When referring here to 'actors', this implies 'innovation actors', i.e. groups of people who are involved in innovation projects and initiatives in the agri-food or forestry sector - farmers, farm workers, agricultural educators, researchers, non-academic experts, public and independent private advisors, supply chain actors, and other actors in agriculture to harness knowledge and information from various sources for improved livelihoods ([LIAISON Glossary](#)).

5.1.2 How is the interactive innovation case connected to these other initiatives (i.e. external actors, stakeholders)?

Please explain whether the interactive innovation case is part of a larger (in)formal network of similar cooperation arrangements, or has more informal contacts with key actors in the relevant area. In the excel file a few extra questions are proposed in order to get to an answer to this question.

5.1.3 What are the key institutions framing this third interaction?

Please fill in the table below. Institutions are commonly known as ‘the rules of the game’ or ‘code of conduct’.

Institutions framing the interactions	At the programme level	At the interactive innovation case level
Formal <i>formal and tangible rules such as laws, regulations, contracts, standards, product specifications and property rights (Woolthuis et al., 2005).</i>	<i>Any rules or regulations that are written down and can be enforced, e.g. guidelines, administrative requirements.</i>	<i>Any type of signed document. This can be a consortium agreement, contract, formal code of conduct, product specifications etc.</i>

5.1.4 How would the interactive innovation case characterise the relationship with the external stakeholders?

With this question we are trying to find out which are the more informal institutions that influence this third interaction. Informal institutions influence social and economic life in a subtle often intangible way (Coenen and Diaz Lopez, 2010). Examples are trust, habits, norms, values, beliefs, types of behaviours traditions, routines and preferences. This can be very subjective and might differ from one respondent to another. Some more questions you could use are provided in the excel file.

5.2 FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

5.2.1 How and when did the interactive innovation case identify the relevant stakeholders?

Please explain the methods and tools the interactive innovation case used to identify the stakeholders they found to be relevant. This could for example include their approach to stakeholder mapping, the role of personal contacts, any difficulties they met in this identification process etc.

5.2.2 How and when were stakeholders involved by the interactive innovation case?

Here we would like to learn whether the interactive innovation case had drafted an a priori ‘stakeholder involvement plan’ or an ‘actor analysis’ or any other formal strategy that set out the timing and objective of the involvement of external actors. If this was not the case, you could explain their own method and whether they think they could have benefited from a more formal approach.

Were there sufficient opportunities for the stakeholders to interact with the interactive innovation case and vice versa? Why (not)?

Please explain whether the frequency and way of interactions with external stakeholders were appropriate or not and why the case study actors perceive them in this way.

5.2.3 Could you characterise the different stakeholders according to their amount of power or influence over and the level of their interest in the interactive innovation case?

Please fill in the table below. You can skip those actor types that are not relevant to your case study.

With ‘power’ or ‘influence’ of a stakeholder, we want to know how much influence the case study actors think a certain stakeholder could have over the results or outcome of their work. This judgement will inevitably be quite subjective and the amount of ‘power’ or ‘influence’ a certain stakeholder has can change over time.

With ‘interest in the results’, we would like the case study actors to estimate how interested certain stakeholders are in the results or outcomes of their work. For example, this could give us indications of their level of motivation to get involved in any stakeholder outreach activities.

Stakeholders: Types	More specifically:	Power or influence (High – Medium – Low)	Interest in the results (High – Medium – Low)
Individual farmers or foresters			
Researchers and R&D departments			
Education			
Support organisations			
Market actors – supply side			
Market actors – demand side			
Civil society			
Administrative bodies			
Other (please specify):			

Looking back, were there any stakeholder which were not directly involved in the interactive innovation case, but which could also be relevant based on the power/interest consideration?

If the case study actors or the external stakeholders could have known in advance, which stakeholders would they have wanted to involve? Which ones would they have involved differently?

5.2.4 Why were stakeholders involved in the interactive innovation case?

Please fill in the table. Some examples of reasons for involvement are: these actors had knowledge or information that was not available within the partnership, key end-user of the innovation, the next player in the supply chain (possible client), an important competitor, holds information on other actors in the system etc.

Stakeholders: Types	Reason for their involvement/Objectives of their involvement <i>(from the perspective of the interactive innovation case)</i>
Individual farmers or foresters	
Researchers and R&D departments	
Education	
Support organisations	
Market actors – supply side	
Market actors – demand side	
Civil society	
Administrative bodies	
Other (please specify):	

5.2.5 Why did stakeholders want to engage in the interactive innovation case?

Please fill in the table. You will only be able to give the point of view of those stakeholders you have interviewed or if case study actors have consistently indicated these stakeholders' motivations.

Stakeholders: Types	Motivation for becoming involved <i>(from the perspective of the stakeholders)</i>
Individual farmers or foresters	
Researchers and R&D departments	
Education	
Support organisations	
Market actors – supply side	
Market actors – demand side	
Civil society	
Administrative bodies	
Other (please specify):	

5.3 GOOD PRACTICES AND FAILURES

5.3.1 Which relevant external actors or stakeholders were not consulted or contacted? Why (not)?

Please explain whether there were any actors or stakeholders not consulted or contacted according to the different actors of the interactive innovation case. Please also elaborate on the possible reasons behind.

5.3.2 How do the interactive innovation case actors value the involvement of the stakeholders?

Please elaborate on the value the different actors of the interactive innovation case attach to the involvement of external actors. You can elaborate here on how useful they found the involvement of stakeholders and what they have learned from their involvement.

5.3.3 How were the inputs of stakeholders used in the interactive innovation case? To which extent did their involvement have an influence over the interactive innovation case?

Please explain the way the results of stakeholder involvement were used by the interactive innovation case. Please also differentiate between different groups of stakeholders in your answer.

5.3.4 What could be the consequences of the interactive innovation case on other actors/stakeholders?

Please explain whether the interactive innovation case could have some consequences for other actors/stakeholders in the agricultural knowledge and innovation system (AKIS). We would like to learn more about possible 'winners' or 'losers' of the outcomes or results of the interactive innovation case. Who will benefit most from their work? Who will be challenged? Who will be more indirectly affected?

5.4 CASE STUDY SPECIFIC ISSUES

If there are any other concerns related to the third interaction for which you could not find any place under the previous questions, please write them down here.

6 FINDINGS FOR INTERACTION 4

The major objectives of the research related to this interaction are to:

1. Identify the type of influence the broader environment ('the bigger picture') has on interactive innovation cases and vice versa;
2. Learn where the interactive innovation cases perceive themselves fitting into the broader environment;
3. Understand which challenges interactive innovation cases are faced with in terms of rules and regulations, norms and social values and how they deal with them.

Explanatory note for Interaction 4

In this fourth interaction, we are looking at everything that has to do with the context or environment the interactive innovation case forms a part of. All findings linked to financing and funding are covered by interaction 1, so here we move beyond these issues. We understand that there will be some overlap as these divisions between the interactions are artificial and purely for analytical reasons. If you are not sure where to put certain findings, you can either contact the WP 4 team or make an informed decision where you think the information fits best.

In this section, we expect to see the findings related to the larger context or environment in which an interactive innovation case is situated. You can imagine this as the bigger picture, which can form an 'enabling environment', thus providing a good and conducive context for (a) the innovation your particular case is working on, and/or (b) the process of co-creation for innovation in a multi-actor partnership. Nevertheless, this context can also pose different types of barriers or challenges, thus forming a 'disabling environment' to either (a) or (b), or both.

More specifically, the 'environment' includes the level of acceptance or openness of a specific context towards innovations, innovative ideas, new ways of cooperation etc. This can be found at:

- *a formal level, e.g. legislation which is changed or adopted in support of innovation or innovative ideas, specific types of tax incentives or subsidies etc.; and*
- *at the informal level such as the available 'mental space' or the willingness to support a different way of working or a shift or evolution in beliefs, values and norms.*

6.1 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

6.1.1 Who are the key actors⁵ in this interaction?

Please fill in the table below. You can find some additional questions to help you fill in the table in the excel file. The key actors in this interaction can be both formally and directly involved in the interactive innovation case, or can be considered a 'stakeholder', meaning individuals/persons or groups served by, affected by, or with a legitimate interest (or stake) at a certain moment in time in the interactive innovation case ([LIAISON Glossary](#)). You can start with the 'light-touch' review results and then continue with your additional gathered data. In this fourth interaction, we look at actors both internal and external to the case which have a role to play in the context or the environment in which the interactive innovation case is situated. This thus includes also those actors which have never been directly or indirectly involved.

Actor types	More specifically:	Name of organisation and sector (public/private)	Opinion/stance on the interactive innovation case If applicable
Individual farmers or foresters	<i>e.g. pioneer farmer, organic farmer</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Researchers or R&D departments	<i>e.g. researchers at institutes or universities, R&D departments</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Education	<i>e.g. primary education, (agricultural) schools, universities in their role as educator</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Support organisations	<i>e.g. advisors, representative of supporting organisations, financial actors (banks, venture capital, business angels), network organisations</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Market actors – supply side	<i>e.g. business, suppliers (e.g. raw materials), manufacturers, service providers</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Market actors – demand side	<i>e.g. business, processing or marketing SME, processing or marketing producer organisation, retailers, consumers and their organisations, other companies (B2B)</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Civil society	<i>e.g. NGOs, local community groups, LEADER groups</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Administrative bodies	<i>e.g. local municipality, regional government, national government, ministries, departments, EU institutions</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>
Others (please specify)	<i>any type of actors that does not fit with the types from above</i>		<i>e.g. supportive, indifferent, competitor, curious</i>

⁵ When referring here to 'actors', this implies 'innovation actors', i.e. groups of people who are involved in innovation projects and initiatives in the agri-food or forestry sector - farmers, farm workers, agricultural educators, researchers, non-academic experts, public and independent private advisors, supply chain actors, and other actors in agriculture to harness knowledge and information from various sources for improved livelihoods ([LIAISON Glossary](#)).

6.1.2 Why are these the key actors in this interaction?

Please explain in a few sentences why these are the key actors in this interaction and who makes this argumentation (is it you as the researcher, was it your contact person, were they multiple respondents?)

6.1.3 What are the key institutions framing this fourth interaction?

Please fill in the table below. Institutions are commonly known as ‘the rules of the game’ or ‘code of conduct’.

Institutions framing the interactions	At the programme level	At the interactive innovation case level
Formal <i>formal and tangible rules such as laws, regulations, contracts, standards, product specifications and property rights (Woolthuis et al., 2005).</i>	<i>Any rules or regulations that are written down and can be enforced, e.g. guidelines, administrative requirements</i>	<i>Any type of signed document. This can be a consortium agreement, contract, formal code of conduct, product specifications etc.</i>

6.1.4 What is the general perception on (co-creation for) innovation in the context/environment the interactive innovation case is situated?

With this question we are trying to find out which the more informal institutions are that influence this third interaction. Informal institutions influence social and economic life in a subtle often intangible way (Coenen and Diaz Lopez, 2010). Examples are trust, habits, norms, values, beliefs, types of behaviours traditions, routines and preferences. This can be very subjective and might differ from one respondent to another. Some more questions you could use are provided in the excel file. For this specific question, you can use interviews with different respondents (actors from within the partnership, policy or project officers, external stakeholders etc.)

6.2 FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

6.2.1 How does the AKIS in which the interactive innovation case is embedded influence the interactive innovation case?

The AKIS is the organisation and interaction of actors, organisations and institutions who use and produce knowledge and innovation for agriculture and interrelated fields. The main players of the AKIS are farmers, advisors, researchers, (farmer) organisations, retailers, media, services, ministries: they all produce and need knowledge. The aim is to create a regional/national innovation ecosystem by enhancing knowledge flows between the AKIS players as well as strengthening links between research and practice. Here we would like to learn whether or not the case study actors see the AKIS as something that has supported them in their work and how they think their case fits into this system. Some extra questions for inspiration can be found in the excel file.

6.2.2 How has (have) the local culture(s) affected the interactive innovation process?

Please explain how the case study actors think local culture or the mix of local cultures had an influence on their work. We understand 'local culture' as the way how people interact with each other on a daily basis, the perception of how business is usually done, the type of behaviour or interactions people find appropriate, acceptable and are comfortable with. The answers here can be very subjective, which is normal. Some extra questions for inspiration can be found in the excel file.

6.2.3 What was the role of external support or external actors (in the form of e.g. innovation support service, external facilitator), if any?

Please explain whether there was a broker or innovation support service involved and how they assisted the case study. If there was no involvement, please answer the next question instead. This is put under interaction 4 as we would like to find out whether there is any support available in the wider context, or whether the interactive innovation case made the explicit choice not to involve external help.

If there was no external involvement in the form of e.g. innovation support service, innovation brokerage, external facilitator, what was the reason and how could their involvement have improved the interactive innovation process?

Please explain why there was no broker or innovation support service involved and what the case study actors think could have been their impact.

6.2.4 What are the expectations for the future of other actors/organisations/businesses in this field? Where would the interactive innovation case put itself in this story?

Please explain whether the case study actors perceive that there are certain expectations towards the future developments among the relevant players in their field of interest (e.g. a specific sector or a geographical area). Furthermore, we would like to learn where the case study fits within this perception, is it in line with the mainstream ideas or rather going into a different direction? Please elaborate on the perception external actors have of the work that is being done in the case study.

6.2.5 Are there clear policy goals (at local, regional, national, European level) in the field/sector the interactive innovation case is working? If yes, which ones? If no, why do they think this is?

Please explain whether there are any relevant policy goals or objectives related to the field or sector the interactive innovation case is working on. Please also elaborate whether these goals or objectives are clear or whether they are interpreted in different ways.

6.3 GOOD PRACTICES AND FAILURES

6.3.1 Were there sufficient opportunities generated to link up with other innovators or pioneers? Why (not)?

Please explain whether the case study actors found that there were sufficient opportunities to meet and link with other innovators and why. You could also elaborate on who should organise or manage these links between innovators.

6.3.2 How did the case study look for or connect with other programmes, strategies or relevant policy domains (if any)?

Please explain whether there were any considerations made on which other sources or types of funding, programmes or strategies already existed. If this was not the case, the answer could include potential funding mechanisms, programmes or strategies with which a link could have been made according to respondents (e.g. actors within the interactive innovation case, from the funding body or from other relevant key informants).

6.3.3 Which types of legislation or policy instruments gave incentives or posed bottlenecks (other than those related to the requirements of the funding mechanism) to the interactive innovation case?

Please explain which bottlenecks and incentives the interactive innovation case identified and how. Answers could include for example that they had to get help from outside for the identification, or that during the consultation with stakeholders some issues arose. You can also explain which potential issues there might arise in the future. Please also elaborate on the impact these bottlenecks had on the interactive innovation case.

6.3.4 Which socio-economic challenges (e.g. lacking market, lack of resources, poverty, inequality) posed bottlenecks or opportunities to the interactive innovation case? In what way?

Please explain the socio-economic context of the interactive innovation case. You could elaborate on whether there is an existing market for the innovation intended by the case study, or whether the existing infrastructure posed any barriers to their way of working, did they gain support in the development of a possible market or infrastructure, were there important opponents or supporters of their work etc. Also, the influence of certain vested interests or the way the agenda is set can be part of the answer here.

6.3.5 Who or what will the interactive innovation case have helped forward in the long run? To what extent?

Please explain what the case study actors perceive to be the long-term impacts of their interactive innovation process on the actors or institutions in the 'environment'. You can also elaborate on what consequences the end of the funding period have on their case, whether they already have next steps in mind, or perhaps they feel that they have accomplished their goals.

6.4 CASE STUDY SPECIFIC ISSUES

If there are any other concerns related to the fourth interaction for which you could not find any place under the previous questions, please write them down here.

7 FINDINGS FOR INTERACTION 5

The major objectives of the research related to this interaction are to:

1. Identify which type of societal/technological/economic/social/ecological challenges the interactive innovation actors aim to tackle and how they think they are achieving this;
2. Understand how the actors of an interactive innovation case perceive their contribution to the future of agriculture, forestry or rural development and how they aim to disseminate their knowledge.

In this interaction we do not aim for a thorough analysis, rather we would like you to pose these more general questions to your respondents. These are, for example, good questions with which to finalise interviews or focus groups.

7.1 WHICH TYPE OF THE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES DO THE CASE STUDY ACTORS THINK THEY HAVE MADE CONTRIBUTIONS TO? TO WHAT EXTENT?

Please fill in the table below. We advise you to ask the general question as posed above and let the respondent answer openly. You can then summarise their answers in this table afterwards.

Societal challenges	Not relevant	Extent of their contribution		
		Low	Medium	High
Depopulation:				
<i>Employment</i>				
<i>Immigration</i>				
Climate change				
Globalisation:				
<i>Competitiveness to market access</i>				
<i>Local identity</i>				
<i>Social empowerment</i>				
Forest fires				
Water management				
Governance				
Empowerment				
Food safety				
Gender inequality				
(Youth) employment generation				
Agricultural paradigm change (<i>for example land</i>				

Societal challenges	Not relevant	Extent of their contribution		
		Low	Medium	High
<i>use change, renewable energy)</i>				
Optimisation of decision-making and planning process				
(New) crop adoption				
Social innovation (<i>please explain what kind of SI</i>)				
Improving the supply / value - chain				
Environmental degradation				
Other (<i>please specify</i>)				

7.2 WHICH PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTIONS DO THE CASE STUDY ACTORS THINK THEY HAVE MADE IN TACKLING CERTAIN SOCIETAL CHALLENGES?

Please explain where the case study actors made very practical contributions in terms of setting a next step towards tackling certain societal challenges. Some inspiration for questions is given in the excel file.

7.3 WHO OR WHAT WILL THE INTERACTIVE INNOVATION CASE HAVE HELPED FORWARD IN THE LONG RUN? TO WHAT EXTENT?

Please explain what the case study actors perceive to be the long-term impacts of their interactive innovation process on the actors or institutions in the 'environment'. You can also elaborate on what consequences the end of the funding period have on their case, whether they already have next steps in mind, or perhaps they feel that they have accomplished their goals.

7.4 WHAT DO THE CASE STUDY ACTORS THINK THEIR WORK WILL MEAN FOR THE FUTURE OF AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND/OR RURAL DEVELOPMENT?

Please explain how case study actors perceive the impact of their work on the bigger picture of their respective area. Some inspiration for questions is given in the excel file.

8 CONCLUSIONS AND KEY FINDINGS

In max. two pages, please write down the key finding of the case study according to you. While in the rest of this document we asked you to let the case study actors speak, here we are asking for your own expert opinion. Please discuss these key findings within your LIAISON project team.

8.1 OVERARCHING KEY FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

8.2 KEY FINDINGS SPECIFIC TO INTERACTION 1

8.3 KEY FINDINGS SPECIFIC TO INTERACTION 2

8.4 KEY FINDINGS SPECIFIC TO INTERACTION 3

8.5 KEY FINDINGS SPECIFIC TO INTERACTION 4

8.6 KEY FINDINGS SPECIFIC TO INTERACTION 5

9 REFLECTIONS BY THE LIAISON PARTNERS

In max. half a page, please reflect on the work you have done during your case study. These reflections can be both made on the level of the content of the case study as on the more practical level (i.e. in conducting interviews, focus groups and in interacting with the case study). Which lessons have you learned? What would you have done differently if you would have to do it again? What was your experience?

10 REFERENCES

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